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HOW TO MEASURE THE PERFORMANCE LEVEL IN COMPETENCY BASED EDUCATION SYSTEM – SOME SUGGESTIONS

P. S. Aithal¹, Mike Dillon², & Suresh Kumar P. M.³

¹College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, INDIA

²Director, Institute of Productivity, Grimsby, UK.

³Department of Social Science, Christ University, Bangalore, INDIA

E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

Abstract

Competence means ability or capability and performance is the proof of competence. The objective of higher education is to impart competency to the learners and the presumption is that those who undergo higher education have acquired competency. As opposed to this, is the credit based system where the grades directly speak what a student has earned through education ?. But the question is how to measure competency among the graduates who pass out. Various indicators are available in Competency Based Education System (CBES). One is employability, i.e., the capability to take-up and performs a job with little of support. However, this is something that is decided by the employer and difficult to set a benchmark. Our competency measurement model suggests that apart from knowledge, specific skills, and experience on a job, other supporting skills like Communication, proficiency in writing, generation of new ideas, preserving a vision in life, desire for learning, and improvement in life, attitude towards life, respect for fellow-beings, and such other qualities could be hugely a measure of competency acquired from education. It may be difficult to quantify, yet it is essential to be considered through a properly developed measuring scale to be given as competency level. In this discussion, an attempt has been made to identify such factors which contributes to competency based education and measuring their performance outcome using a newly suggested model based on different ranking scales.

Keywords : CBES, Competency based education, Outcome based education, Performance level, Competency Measurement model, Competency Measurement Scales.

1. INTRODUCTION :

The objective of higher education is to develop systematic thinking ability of the students by means of enhancing knowledge, skills, and experience which in turn expected to increase the confidence of the solving problems of self and society [1]. In the process of imparting higher education, two models are considered to be relevant in the current century which are (1) Conventional classroom based education model [2-4] and (2) Technology supported online ubiquitous education model [5, 6, 7]. The two higher education systems which are expected to be attractive to the learners are Choice Based Credit system (CBCS) and Competency based Education system (CBES) [8].

Presently Indian higher education system follows choice based credit system of assessment and evaluation. A credit system is a systematic way of describing an educational programme by attaching credits to its components. The credits in higher education systems may be based on different parameters, such as student workload, learning outcomes and contact hours. University Grants Commission has come up with the Choice Based Credit System (CBCS), a programme in which the students while choosing the prescribed course, which is the core, can opt for any elective or minor or soft skill courses and the entire assessment is graded, based on a credit system. The CBCS provides choice for students to select the elective components in any other institution as well.

Competency-Based Credit System (CBES) is a significant improvement in CBCS model. It provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education by means of providing a proper direction while choosing the subjects, and in the assessment. Competency-based programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit. It allows students to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills and experience as per the demands of the industry to the extent decided by the institution. A student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses to be taught by approved faculty members. Instead, in CBES, a student has to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content [6, 8]. This model allows students to work and learn anywhere and as per the curriculum of the University/Higher education institution where they enrolled for their courses have to develop specific competency levels and get a graduation certificate. The evaluation part of Competency based education system is most challenging and there is no hard and fast method as well as the rating scale accepted by universally exists today. Competency based education system is not a new concept and is under discussion since 1970 [10-17]. Due to the limitations involved in the evaluation and distribution of scores/ rating of outcomes, CBES model in higher education could not become popular and not adopted in most of the universities.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER :

This conceptual paper based on explorative research has the following objectives :

- (1) To analyse the objectives of competency based education system (CBES).
- (2) To analyse the distinctive features of CBES.
- (3) To study the factors which contribute to competency based education and measuring their performance outcome.
- (4) Suggestions to effective implementation of CBES based on critical analysis.

3. COMPETENCY BASED EDUCATION SYSTEM –OBJECTIVES :

Competence means ability or capability and performance is the proof of competence. The objective of higher education is to impart competency to the learners and the presumption is that those who undergo higher education have acquired competency. As opposed to this, is the credit based system where the grades directly speak what a student has earned through education?. But the question is how to measure competency among the graduates who want to pass out. However, this is something that is decided by the employer and difficult to set a

benchmark at university level during evaluation for offering graduation certificate. In this paper, we have proposed two grading methods based on a modified 1-10 rating scale and the other is a modified Likert scale model to measure and express competency of a graduate in a given subject/area. In its final form, the Likert Scale is a five or seven-point scale depending on the rigorousness of the evaluation which is used to allow the evaluator to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement related to competency level. Based on the Likert scale competency indicator, the employability, i.e., the capability to take-up and performs a job by a graduate under consideration with little of support from other members of the organization can be judged.

4. FEATURES OF CBES :

CBES involves educating a student in order to improve the competency of performance in one or more fields of specializations. This includes enhancing his knowledge, skills, and experience along with ethical aspects of doing things systematically to the expectations of the industry. The evaluation of competency should focus on developing the progress report of the candidate periodically to report the speed of learning and achieving the different levels of competency. Such an evaluation process and outcome is called competency rating and reporting. The distinctive features of CBES are :

- (1) Competency based education system focus on building and measuring some pre-defined competency in performing a specified task efficiently and effectively.
- (2) It provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education by means of providing a proper direction while choosing the subjects, and in the assessment.
- (3) Competency-based programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit.
- (4) It allows students to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills, and experience as per the demands of the industry to the extent decided by the institution.
- (5) A student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses to be taught by approved faculty members. Instead, in CBES, a student has to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content.
- (6) The system allows a student to choose any number of areas where he/she is interested to enhance the skills required to do a particular job with learned required competency.

5. PERFORMANCE LEVEL MEASUREMENT IN CBES :

Competency based education system focus on developing working skills on a particular set of jobs during a time frame. These working skills called competency comprises of working knowledge, expertise, and smartness to complete the job/jobs. Various teaching-learning methods including classroom teaching, laboratory based learning, experiential learning, experimental learning, online learning, internship based projects, fieldwork practicum etc. are considered as effective methods to be adopted in competency based education system. There are various factors contributes to competency based education and measuring their performance outcome. Our competency measurement model suggests that apart from knowledge, specific skills, and experience on a job, other supporting skills like Communication, proficiency in writing, generation of new ideas, preserving a vision in life,

desire for learning and improvement in life, attitude towards life, respect for fellow-beings, self-control and such other qualities could be hugely a measure of competency acquired from education. Table 1 lists such factors which contribute to the competency and their expected performance outcome.

Table 1 : Factors which contributes to competency and their expected performance outcome.

S. No.	Factors contributing to the Competency in CBES	Expected Performance Outcome
1	Communication	Rapid Action
2	Proficiency in writing	Quick response with accuracy
3	Generation of new ideas	Innovation & Efficiency
4	Preserving a vision in life,	Adaptability & Value addition
5	Desire for learning and improvement in life	Pro-activeness
6	Attitude towards life	Positive view
7	Respect for fellow-beings	Increased co-operation
8	Self-control	Courage in action

Various rating scales have been used in the past to measure intangible quantities like attitude, feelings, qualities, perception, love, affection, happiness, pain, satisfaction, status, talent, knowledge, etc. Two popular rating scales used to give an opinion about a product, service, taste, and even competency of a person to do a given task are Likert scale and 1-10 rating scales (sometimes 0-10 scale). The Choice Based Credit System has modified 1-10 rating scale for allotting grade points with grade levels between Outstanding to Fail as shown in table 2.

Table 2: Allotment grades in modified 1-10 rating scale in Choice Based Credit system

S. No.	Letter Grade	Grade Level	Grade Point
1	O	Outstanding	10
2	A+	Excellent	9
3	A	Very good	8
4	B+	Good	7
5	B	Above Average	6
6	C	Average	5
7	P	Pass	4
8	F	Fail	0
9	Ab	Absent	0

The proposed Competency Based Grading system is a Measurement system to grade the level of competency and its equivalent points instead of offering credits. The evaluation system and grading pattern may contain any model of allocating grading levels and grade points based on student competency shown at the time of evaluation. Here, we propose two models of competency grading.

5.1 Models for Competency Grading System :

Model 1 for Competency Reporting:

This model is based in 1-10 rating scale. This is an extension of choice based credit system grading. Here, the competency level of a student under evaluation is graded using grade points anywhere between one to ten. Absent to evaluation process by the respective student is graded as zero. Depending on evaluator's assessment on a candidate, grading level and corresponding grading point should be determined. Table 3 lists various competency levels and the corresponding grade points.

Table 3 : Competency rating model in a given skill based on 1-10 rating scale

S. No.	Competency Level	Grade Point
1	Outstanding	10
2	Excellent	9
3	Very good	8
4	Good	7
5	Above Average	6
6	Average	5
7	Below Average	4
8	Weak	3
9	Very Weak	2
10	Extremely Weak	1
11	Absent	0

Model 2 for Competency Reporting:

Even if competency is an intangible property, it can be measurable to some extent through various traits. To measure the competency of a graduate in any area/field, we propose another model which is a modified Likert scale model [18]. This scale or metric supports to measure and express the competency of a graduate in a given subject/area to a greater extent in a systematic way. In its final form, this scale is a seven point scale depending on the rigorousness of the evaluation which is used to allow the evaluator to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement related to competency level. Based on this modified Likert scale competency indicator, the employability, i.e., the capability to take-up and performs a job by a graduate under consideration with little of support from other members of the organization can be judged. This model is based on 7 point Likert Scale. Here, seven grades are allotted based on a student's competency on a given skill or subject. The evaluator, through demonstration, shall decide the competency level and fix it to any deserved level and the grade points should be allotted accordingly. In this model, the competency reporting system may follow either optimistic assessment by using positive scale, a most likely assessment scale called neutral scale, or a pessimistic assessment model by using negative scale.

(1) Positive Scale :

This is an optimistic /positive assessment scale used to measure and report the strength of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

(2) Neutral Scale :

This is a neutral most-likely assessment scale used to measure and report the abilities of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

(3) Negative Scale :

This is a negative assessment scale used to measure and report the weakness of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

Table 4 : Competency rating model based on positive modified Likert Scale rating for a given skill

S. No.	Competency Level	Grading	Grade Point
1	Outstanding		7
2	Excellent		6
3	Very good		5
4	Good		4
5	Above Average		3
6	Average		2
7	Below Average		1

Table 5 : Competency rating model based on neutral modified Likert Scale rating for a given skill

S. No.	Competency Level	Grading	Grade Point
1	Very good		3
2	Good		2
3	Above Average		1
4	Average		0
5	Below Average		-1
6	Weak		-2
7	Very Weak		-3
8	Absent		-

Table 6 : Competency rating model based on negative modified Likert Scale rating

S. No.	Competency Level	Grading	Grade Point
1	Average		-1
2	Below Average		-2
3	Low		-3
4	Weak		-4
5	Very Weak		-5
6	Extremely Weak		-6
7	Not qualified		-7
8	Qualified		0

5.2 Complete Performance Measurement Model based on above Scales :

The competency based performance measurement format consists of listing of various skills required to perform a job satisfactorily and the competency grading level of a candidate along with corresponding grade point. This also includes the time taken by the candidate to reach the required competent level as shown in Competency Report format given in table 7.

Table 7 : Competency Report format for a Job _____

S.No.	Skills Required for the Job	Competency Grading level	Grade Point	Time taken to reach the level
1	Knowledge			
2	Working skills			
3	Expertise level			
4	Communication			
5	Proficiency in writing			
6	Generation of new ideas			
7	Preserving a vision in life			
8	Desire for learning and improvement in life			
9	Attitude towards life			
10	Respect for fellow-beings			
11	Self-control			

Table 8 : Example of competency report based on positive scale for Accounting job

Name : Ashok B.		Roll No. : 2019K29		DOB:04/04'1999
S.No.	Skills Required for the Job	Competency Grading level	Grade Point	Time taken to reach the level
1	Knowledge	Very good	5	12 months
2	Working skills	Good	4	18 months
3	Expertise level	Excellent	6	12 months
4	Communication	Average	2	08 months
5	Proficiency in writing	Very good	5	18 months
6	Generation of new ideas	Excellent	6	18 months
7	Preserving a vision in life	Average	2	24 months
8	Desire for learning and improvement in life	Excellent	6	12 months
9	Attitude towards life	Average	2	18 months
10	Respect for fellow-beings	Below Average	1	18 months
11	Self-control	Good	4	12 months

6. CONCLUSION :

CBES involves developing various employability skills of a student in order to improve the competency of performance in one or more fields of specializations. In this system, apart from enhancing the knowledge, skills, and experience along with ethical aspects, of doing things systematically to the expectations of the industry. CBES in higher education provides a

proper direction of required skills to be developed by a student while choosing the subjects, and the assessment. Competency-based education programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit. In this system, students have to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills and experience. CBES is a continuous improvement program for individuals and as per the demands of the industry. Since a student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses, but to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content. Hence the model allows students to work and learn anywhere and have to develop specific competency levels and get a graduation certificate. The evaluation part of Competency based education system is discussed in this paper and an appropriate solution of grading model based on developed competency is proposed.

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